

Gender Norms and Structural Barriers to
Use of HIV Prevention in Unmarried and Married
Young Women in Manicaland, Zimbabwe:
An HIV Prevention Cascade Analysis

EXTENDED DATA:

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

TABLE S1 Survey questions for inclusion in the priority populations for HIV prevention in unmarried and married AGYW

Priority population	Sexual behaviour	Survey question	Response
Unmarried AGYW at HIV risk	Not currently married; <i>and ...</i>	'Have you ever been married or in a long-term (≥ 12 months) or cohabiting relationship?' <i>or, if YES ...</i>	'No'
		'Are you currently widowed, divorced or separated from your most recent spouse or partner?'	'Yes'
	Started sex; <i>and ...</i>	'How old were you when you had sex for the first time?'	<i>Not</i> 'Not yet had sex'
	Sexually-active in the last 12 months	'How many days is it since you last had sex?'	<i>Not</i> 'More than 1 year'
Married AGYW at HIV risk	Currently married; <i>and at least one of:</i>	'Have you ever been married or in a long-term (≥ 12 months) or cohabiting relationship?'	'Yes'
	AGYW has other sexual partners	'How many different sexual partners has you had in the last 12 months?' <i>or ...</i> 'How many of the sexual partners you had in the last 12 months were non-regular partners?'	'>1' ' ≥ 1 '
	Spouse has other sexual partners	'If you took a guess, how many partners other than yourself (and any co-wives) do you think your current spouse/partner has had in the last 12 months?'	' ≥ 1 '
	Spouse is HIV-positive	'Do you know if this partner is HIV-positive now?'	'Yes - Infected'

TABLE S2 Survey questions used to measure the main bars in the condom HIV prevention cascades for unmarried and married AGYW

Cascade bar	Denominator	Numerator	Response
		Survey question	
Motivation ¹	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention ²	'Do you want to use condoms with your non-regular/regular partner if they were freely accessible to you?'	'YES'
Access ¹	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention ² <i>and</i> ... Who meet the criteria for inclusion in the motivation bar	Conditions met for one or more of the explanatory factors (sub-bars) for having access to condoms ³	NA
Effective use	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention ² <i>and</i> ... Who meet the criteria for inclusion in the motivation and access bars		'YES'
Condom use at last sex (Figure 6)	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention ²	'Did you use a condom throughout the last time you had sex?'	'YES'

NOTES: ¹All AGYW who reported having used condoms throughout the last time they had sex were assumed to have been motivated and had access to use them;

²Table S1; ³Table S3.

TABLE S3 Survey questions used to measure the explanatory factors (sub-bars) in the extended condom HIV prevention cascades for unmarried and married AGYW

Explanatory factor	Denominator	Numerator Survey question	Response
Motivation barriers	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention but not meeting the motivation criteria ¹		
Lack of knowledge		<i>At least one of ...</i> 'What methods of HIV prevention have you heard about?'	Male condoms not mentioned
Lack of risk perception		'By how much do you think male condoms reduce a person's risk of getting HIV infection?' 'What are the chances that you are infected with HIV now?'	'<80%' or 'Don't know' Not 'Certain or almost certain'
Perceived negative consequences		<i>and ...</i> 'What are the chances that you will become infected with HIV in the next 12 months if you are not infected now but continue with your current behaviour?'	Not 'Certain or almost certain' or 'High'
Lack of social acceptability		'What factors were/are important in encouraging or discouraging you to use male condoms?' 'Which people's views were/are important in discouraging you from using male condoms?' or 'Are many of your friends (or their partners) using male condoms?'	'Own sexual pleasure' 'Friends/community views' 'No' or "Don't know"
Access barriers	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention who meet the motivation criteria ¹ but not the access criteria ¹		
Not available		Male condoms assumed to be fully available in the study areas	NA
Not affordable		'What factors make it impractical or unsuitable for someone like you to access male condoms?'	'High costs' ²
Lack of acceptable provision		'What factors make it impractical or unsuitable for someone like you to access male condoms?'	'Lack of privacy /confidentiality' or 'Embarrassed to go/ask'
Not easily accessible		'If/when you want to use male condoms, do you know a place where someone like you can easily get them?' <i>or</i> 'Do you feel able to access male condoms from the following places?' <i>or</i> 'What factors make it impractical or unsuitable for someone like you to access male condoms?'	'No' No places mentioned ³ 'Limited opening hours' or 'Distance /travel difficulties'
Effective use barriers	AGYW in the priority population for HIV prevention who meet the motivation and access criteria ¹ but not the criteria for effective use ¹		
Lacks practical skills		'Have you ever received instructions or counselling on how to use male condoms?' <i>or</i> 'Has a male condom ever broken when you were using it?' <i>and</i> 'What do you do when male condoms break?'	'No' 'Yes' 'Continue without replacing the condom'
Partner disapproval		'Does your partner ⁴ disapprove if you use male condoms?' <i>or</i> 'Which people's views were/are important in encouraging or discouraging you to use male condoms?'	'Yes' 'Partner's sexual pleasure'
Lacks social skills		'Which people's views were/are important in encouraging or discouraging you to use male condoms?'	'Partner's view' or 'Partner will think I have HIV or other partners'
Low self-efficacy		'Are you able to discuss using male condoms with your partner ⁴ ?' <i>or</i> 'If your partner ⁴ doesn't want to use condoms, are you able to refuse to have sex with him?' 'Please tell me whether you strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree or strongly agree with the following statements ...' 'I am confident I can use male condoms if I wanted to' 'I am confident I can use male condoms if I wanted to even if I have to use them every time'	'No' 'No' or 'Don't know' 'Strongly disagree or disagree' with either statement

NOTES: ¹Table S2; ²Mentioned spontaneously or when probed; ³Places asked in survey question: Heath clinic, Community-based distributor, Bars/beerhalls, Shops, Your sexual partner(s), F and Other; ⁴Non-regular partners for unmarried AGYW and married AGYW with non-regular partners; regular partner for married AGYW with partner who is HIV-positive or has other partners

TABLE S4 Survey questions used to measure gender norms and other structural barriers to condom use by AGYW

Structural barrier	Survey question	Response
Community disapproval	'Which people's views were/are important in discouraging you from using male condoms?'	'Friends/ community views'
Family disapproval	'Which people's views were/are important in discouraging you from using male condoms?'	'Parents or family elders'
Religious leader disapproval	'Which people's views were/are important in discouraging you from using male condoms?'	'Religious leaders (beliefs)'
Friends not using condoms	'Are many of your friends (or their partners) using male condoms?'	'No' or "Don't know"
Pre-marital sex stigma	'What factors make it impractical or unsuitable for someone like you to access male condoms?'	"Embarrassed to go/ask"
Condoms in marriage stigma	'In what circumstances do you think it is acceptable for a husband and wife to use condoms?'	'Always' ¹
HIV stigma (perceived)	'Which people's views were/are important in discouraging you from using male condoms?'	'Friends/ community will think I have HIV'
Intimate partner violence	'Have you experienced any of the following with a male intimate partner in the last 12 months?' 'Slapped you or threw something at you that could hurt you' 'Pushed or shoved you' 'Hit you with a fist or something else that could hurt you' 'Kicked or dragged you or beat you up' 'Choked or burnt you' 'Threatened or used a gun, knife or other weapon against you' 'Physically forced you to have sexual intercourse against your will' 'Forced you to do something sexual you found degrading or humiliating' 'Made you afraid of what would happen if you did not have sexual intercourse'	'Yes' to ≥1 of these forms of violence

NOTES: ¹Other circumstances that were asked about listed in Table 2.

Table S5 Comparison of community members' views on young women having sex before marriage by socio-demographic characteristics, Manicaland, Zimbabwe, 2018-2019

Characteristic	Males					Females				
	Sex before marriage acceptable			Test for difference		Sex before marriage acceptable			Test for difference	
	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p
Age-group										
15-19	381	1029	(37.0)	0.66 (0.53-0.82)	<0.001	321	1184	(27.1)	0.82 (0.67-1.01)	0.066
20-24	307	693	(44.3)	1	-	336	1043	(32.2)	1	-
25-29	215	485	(44.3)	1.29 (1.00-1.67)	0.053	183	551	(33.2)	0.99 (0.79-1.24)	0.94
30-34	155	352	(44.0)	1.45 (1.07-1.97)	0.017	192	596	(32.2)	0.93 (0.74-1.17)	0.55
35-44	282	623	(45.3)	1.62 (1.20-2.17)	0.001	301	946	(31.8)	0.91 (0.73-1.13)	0.38
45-54	192	426	(45.1)	1.75 (1.26-2.44)	0.001	171	592	(28.9)	0.80 (0.62-1.03)	0.089
55+	198	466	(42.5)	1.53 (1.08-2.17)	0.017	209	817	(25.6)	0.82 (0.61-1.09)	0.18
Residence										
Village	523	1282	(40.8)	1		661	1916	(34.5)	1	
Agricultural estate	651	1247	(52.2)	1.70 (1.42-2.04)	<0.001	330	1151	(28.7)	0.74 (0.62-0.87)	<0.001
Small town	356	950	(37.5)	0.92 (0.76-1.11)	0.39	424	1654	(25.6)	0.64 (0.55-0.76)	<0.001
City (high density)	200	595	(33.6)	0.80 (0.62-1.02)	0.073	298	1008	(29.6)	0.78 (0.64-0.96)	0.019
School education										
None	50	90	(55.6)	1		39	170	(22.9)	1	
Primary	239	562	(42.5)	0.61 (0.38-0.97)	0.037	375	1368	(27.4)	1.09 (0.74-1.61)	0.65
Secondary	1342	3190	(42.1)	0.63 (0.40-0.99)	0.043	1186	3883	(30.5)	1.24 (0.84-1.84)	0.29
Higher	99	232	(42.7)	0.61 (0.36-1.05)	0.073	113	308	(36.7)	1.65 (1.03-2.64)	0.036
Church										
Protestant	411	954	(43.1)	1		390	1355	(28.8)	1	
Traditional	2	3	(66.7)	3.90 (0.34-44.4)	0.27	12	36	(33.3)	1.51 (0.74-3.08)	0.26
None	250	562	(44.5)	0.88 (0.70-1.11)	0.29	46	127	(36.2)	1.66 (1.11-2.47)	0.013
Roman Catholic	183	396	(46.2)	1.20 (0.94-1.53)	0.14	162	533	(30.4)	1.08 (0.86-1.35)	0.51
Pentecostal	271	667	(40.6)	0.89 (0.72-1.10)	0.28	398	1300	(30.6)	1.11 (0.93-1.32)	0.26
Apostolic	417	1007	(41.4)	0.92 (0.76-1.11)	0.39	474	1624	(29.2)	1.04 (0.89-1.23)	0.60
Islam	16	37	(43.2)	0.83 (0.42-1.65)	0.60	18	63	(28.6)	1.17 (0.66-2.08)	0.58
Zionist	11	25	(44.0)	1.22 (0.53-2.80)	0.64	19	57	(33.3)	1.17 (0.66-2.07)	0.58
Other	169	423	(40.0)	0.96 (0.75-1.22)	0.72	194	634	(30.6)	1.08 (0.88-1.33)	0.36
Marital status										
Currently married	882	2146	(41.1)	0.47 (0.36-0.59)	<0.001	1013	3244	(31.2)	1.14 (0.95-1.36)	0.17
Never married	739	1707	(43.3)	1		369	1343	(27.5)	1	
Divorced or separated	67	148	(45.3)	0.56 (0.38-0.84)	0.005	179	517	(34.6)	1.37 (1.07-1.76)	0.014
Widowed	42	73	(57.5)	0.89 (0.51-1.57)	0.68	152	625	(24.3)	0.95 (0.72-1.26)	0.72
Poverty quintile										
Poorest	147	384	(38.3)	1		169	553	(30.6)	1	
Second poorest	890	1930	(46.1)	1.25 (0.98-1.59)	0.069	735	2417	(30.4)	1.04 (0.84-1.28)	0.71
Third poorest	354	895	(39.6)	1.06 (0.81-1.38)	0.66	405	1321	(30.7)	1.09 (0.86-1.37)	0.47
Fourth poorest	310	813	(38.1)	1.18 (0.89-1.59)	0.25	378	1350	(28.0)	0.98 (0.76-1.26)	0.87
Least poor	29	52	(55.8)	2.48 (1.34-4.62)	0.004	26	88	(29.5)	1.04 (0.62-1.74)	0.89
Relationship to 15-24yr woman										
Father	110	298	(36.9)	0.67 (0.51-0.88)	0.004	282	889	(31.7)	1.11 (0.92-1.33)	0.27
Sibling	301	890	(33.8)	0.63 (0.53-0.75)	<0.001	420	1353	(31.0)	1.14 (0.98-1.33)	0.075
Uncle	85	204	(41.7)	0.78 (0.58-1.06)	0.11	137	373	(36.7)	1.34 (1.06-1.69)	0.013
Grandparent	25	81	(30.9)	0.47 (0.28-0.80)	0.005	80	345	(23.2)	0.87 (0.63-1.19)	0.37
Spouse or regular partner	187	446	(41.9)	0.94 (0.72-1.21)	0.48	-	-	-	-	-
Unrelated	1022	2155	(47.4)	1		794	2769	(28.7)	1	
Community role										
Chief or Headman	18	46	(39.1)	0.90 (0.48-1.68)	0.74	2	8	(25.0)	0.98 (0.19-4.93)	0.98
Church leader	21	75	(28.0)	0.62 (0.36-1.04)	0.072	106	334	(31.7)	1.05 (0.82-1.34)	0.72
Teacher	24	50	(48.0)	1.34 (0.71-2.53)	0.35	24	71	(33.8)	0.96 (0.56-1.62)	0.87
Doctor or nurse	1	3	(33.3)	0.91 (0.08-10.2)	0.94	7	16	(43.8)	1.85 (0.67-5.15)	0.24
Village healthworker	1	2	(50.0)	1.00 (0.05-18.2)	1.00	7	25	(28.0)	0.89 (0.36-2.17)	0.80
Other	21	58	(36.2)	0.93 (0.53-1.64)	0.81	6	18	(33.3)	1.12 (0.41-3.03)	0.84
None	1644	3840	(42.8)	1		1561	5257	(29.7)	1	
CBO participation										
Yes	689	1828	(37.7)	0.77 (0.67-0.88)	<0.001	1205	3784	(31.8)	1.34 (1.18-1.52)	<0.001
No	1041	2246	(46.3)	1		508	1945	(26.1)	1	
HIV status										
Uninfected	1516	3555	(42.6)	1		1454	4849	(30.0)	1	
Infected	145	331	(43.8)	0.90 (0.70-1.15)	0.39	196	604	(32.5)	1.15 (0.95-1.40)	0.15
Unknown	69	188	(36.7)	0.85 (0.62-1.18)	0.33	196	604	(32.5)	0.78 (0.58-1.05)	0.10

* Odds ratios from fully-adjusted multivariable logistic regression models.

Table S6 Comparison of community members' views on telling daughters about condoms by socio-demographic characteristics, Manicaland, Zimbabwe, 2018-2019

Characteristic	Males					Females				
	Tell daughter about condoms (agreement)			Test for difference		Tell daughter about condoms (agreement)			Test for difference	
	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p
Age-group										
15-19	543	1029	(52.8)	0.68 (0.55-0.84)	<0.001	430	1184	(36.3)	0.64 (0.53-0.78)	<0.001
20-24	425	693	(61.3)	1	-	506	1043	(48.5)	1	-
25-29	315	485	(64.9)	1.29 (0.99-1.68)	0.055	274	551	(49.7)	0.98 (0.82-1.17)	0.80
30-34	220	352	(62.5)	1.25 (0.92-1.69)	0.16	286	596	(48.0)	0.98 (0.82-1.17)	0.80
35-44	377	623	(60.5)	1.14 (0.85-1.53)	0.38	457	946	(48.3)	0.91 (0.74-1.11)	0.33
45-54	268	426	(62.9)	1.15 (0.83-1.61)	0.40	262	592	(44.3)	0.73 (0.58-0.93)	0.011
55+	247	466	(53.0)	0.92 (0.65-1.30)	0.64	225	817	(27.5)	0.46 (0.35-0.61)	<0.001
Residence										
Village	722	1282	(56.3)	1		769	1916	(40.1)	1	
Agricultural estate	754	1247	(60.5)	1.17 (0.97-1.40)	0.096	476	1151	(41.4)	1.01 (0.86-1.19)	0.88
Small town	547	950	(57.6)	0.99 (0.82-1.20)	0.92	646	1654	(39.1)	0.83 (0.71-0.97)	0.018
City (high density)	372	595	(62.5)	1.07 (0.83-1.37)	0.61	549	1008	(54.5)	1.56 (1.28-1.89)	<0.001
School education										
None	44	90	(48.9)	1		43	170	(25.3)	1	
Primary	319	562	(56.8)	1.57 (0.98-2.51)	0.059	474	1368	(34.6)	1.49 (1.02-2.18)	0.04
Secondary	1871	3190	(58.7)	1.49 (0.95-2.34)	0.085	1746	3883	(45.0)	1.87 (1.27-2.75)	0.001
Higher	161	232	(69.4)	1.98 (1.15-3.42)	0.014	177	308	(57.5)	2.84 (1.80-4.49)	<0.001
Church										
Protestant	593	954	(62.2)	1		585	1355	(43.2)	1	
Traditional	1	3	(33.3)	0.31 (0.03-3.59)	0.35	21	36	(58.3)	1.53 (0.76-3.10)	0.24
None	339	562	(60.3)	0.78 (0.62-0.98)	0.036	67	127	(52.8)	1.50 (1.02-2.21)	0.038
Roman Catholic	234	396	(59.1)	0.94 (0.73-1.20)	0.62	225	533	(42.2)	1.04 (0.84-1.28)	0.72
Pentecostal	416	667	(62.4)	1.01 (0.81-1.25)	0.96	600	1300	(46.2)	0.96 (0.82-1.13)	0.65
Apostolic	541	1007	(53.7)	0.75 (0.62-0.90)	0.003	638	1624	(39.3)	0.83 (0.71-0.97)	0.018
Islam	21	37	(56.8)	0.74 (0.37-1.48)	0.40	26	63	(41.3)	0.99 (0.58-1.69)	0.98
Zionist	15	25	(60.0)	0.92 (0.40-2.11)	0.84	23	57	(40.4)	0.99 (0.58-1.69)	0.98
Other	235	423	(55.6)	0.76 (0.60-0.97)	0.027	255	634	(40.2)	0.79 (0.65-0.95)	0.015
Marital status										
Currently married	1255	2146	(58.5)	0.69 (0.54-0.88)	0.003	1431	3244	(44.1)	1.06 (0.90-1.26)	0.50
Never married	993	1707	(58.2)	1		527	1343	(39.2)	1	
Divorced or separated	104	148	(70.3)	1.18 (0.77-1.80)	0.44	261	517	(50.5)	1.37 (1.08-1.74)	0.010
Widowed	43	73	(58.9)	0.98 (0.55-1.74)	0.95	221	625	(35.4)	1.23 (0.94-1.60)	0.13
Poverty quintile										
Poorest	212	384	(55.2)	1		219	553	(39.6)	1	
Second poorest	1101	1930	(57.0)	0.97 (0.76-1.22)	0.78	945	2417	(39.1)	1.01 (0.83-1.22)	0.95
Third poorest	519	895	(58.0)	1.02 (0.79-1.33)	0.87	567	1321	(42.9)	1.01 (0.82-1.26)	0.90
Fourth poorest	526	813	(64.7)	1.37 (1.03-1.84)	0.031	663	1350	(49.1)	0.96 (0.76-1.21)	0.73
Least poor	37	52	(71.2)	1.86 (0.96-3.60)	0.068	46	88	(52.3)	0.99 (0.61-1.59)	0.96
Relationship to 15-24yr woman										
Parent	187	298	(62.8)	1.18 (0.90-1.56)	0.240	403	889	(45.3)	1.08 (0.91-1.29)	0.38
Sibling	492	890	(55.3)	0.84 (0.71-1.00)	0.047	583	1353	(43.1)	0.99 (0.86-1.14)	0.94
Uncle	98	204	(48.0)	0.57 (0.42-0.76)	<0.001	177	373	(47.5)	1.06 (0.85-1.33)	0.61
Grandparent	30	81	(37.0)	0.52 (0.31-0.86)	0.011	87	345	(25.2)	0.82 (0.60-1.12)	0.21
Spouse or regular partner	272	446	(61.0)	1.06 (0.82-1.38)	0.66	-	-	-	-	-
Unrelated	1316	2155	(61.1)	1		1190	2769	(43.0)	1	
Community role										
Chief or Headman	24	46	(52.2)	0.92 (0.50-1.70)	0.80	2	8	(25.0)	0.75 (0.15-3.86)	0.73
Church leader	39	75	(52.0)	0.98 (0.60-1.58)	0.92	163	334	(48.8)	1.30 (1.03-1.64)	0.029
Teacher	39	50	(78.0)	2.39 (1.14-5.03)	0.022	35	71	(49.3)	0.87 (0.53-1.44)	0.59
Doctor or nurse	2	3	(66.7)	0.91 (0.08-10.4)	0.94	10	16	(62.5)	1.96 (0.68-5.68)	0.21
Village healthworker	1	2	(50.0)	-		18	25	(72.0)	4.11 (1.66-10.2)	0.002
Other	36	58	(62.1)	1.32 (0.75-2.31)	0.34	8	18	(44.4)	0.98 (0.37-2.60)	0.97
None	2254	3840	(58.7)	1		2204	5257	(41.9)	1	
CBO participation										
Yes	956	1828	(52.3)	0.62 (0.54-0.70)	<0.001	1654	3784	(43.7)	1.28 (1.14-1.45)	<0.001
No	1439	2246	(64.1)	1		786	1945	(40.4)	1	
HIV status										
Uninfected	2073	3555	(58.3)	1		2014	4849	(41.5)	1	
Infected	226	331	(68.3)	1.47 (1.13-1.90)	0.004	315	604	(52.2)	1.46 (1.21-1.76)	<0.001
Unknown	96	188	(51.1)	0.67 (0.49-0.92)	0.014	111	276	(40.2)	0.94 (0.72-1.23)	0.66

* Odds ratios from fully-adjusted multivariable logistic regression models.

Table S7 Comparison of community members' views on condoms being made available at schools by socio-demographic characteristics, Manicaland, Zimbabwe, 2018-2019

Characteristic	Males					Females				
	Sex before marriage acceptable			Test for difference		Sex before marriage acceptable			Test for difference	
	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p
Age-group										
15-19	464	1029	(45.1)	0.59 (0.48-0.73)	<0.001	426	1184	(36.0)	0.56 (0.46-0.68)	<0.001
20-24	411	693	(59.3)	1	-	543	1043	(52.1)	1	-
25-29	293	485	(60.4)	0.98 (0.76-1.26)	0.87	306	551	(55.5)	1.17 (0.95-1.45)	0.15
30-39	194	352	(55.1)	0.80 (0.59-1.08)	0.15	330	596	(55.4)	1.10 (0.989-1.36)	0.39
35-44	350	623	(56.2)	0.80 (0.60-1.07)	0.13	526	946	(55.6)	1.05 (0.86-1.29)	0.61
45-54	223	426	(52.3)	0.63 (0.45-0.87)	0.005	315	592	(53.2)	0.93 (0.74-1.18)	0.59
55+	216	466	(46.4)	0.60 (0.43-0.85)	0.004	311	817	(38.1)	0.64 (0.49-0.84)	0.001
Residence										
Village	618	1282	(48.2)	1		880	1916	(45.9)	1	
Agricultural estate	730	1247	(58.5)	1.31 (1.10-1.56)	0.003	523	1151	(45.4)	0.95 (0.81-1.12)	0.53
Small town	501	950	(52.7)	1.04 (0.86-1.25)	0.75	782	1654	(47.3)	1.00 (0.86-1.16)	1.00
City (high density)	302	595	(50.8)	0.83 (0.65-1.05)	0.12	572	1008	(56.7)	1.52 (1.25-1.85)	<0.001
School education										
None	35	90	(38.9)	1		61	170	(35.9)	1	
Primary	290	562	(51.6)	1.60 (1.00-2.56)	0.051	584	1368	(42.7)	1.27 (0.90-1.79)	0.17
Secondary	1691	3190	(53.0)	1.55 (0.99-2.45)	0.058	1936	3883	(49.9)	1.57 (1.11-2.24)	0.012
Higher	135	232	(58.2)	1.88 (1.09-3.22)	0.022	176	308	(57.1)	1.73 (1.13-2.65)	0.012
Church										
Protestant	462	954	(48.4)	1		676	1355	(49.9)	1	
Traditional	3	3	(100.0)	-		17	36	(47.2)	0.76 (0.38-1.52)	0.43
None	318	562	(56.6)	1.17 (0.93-1.46)	0.18	65	127	(51.2)	0.96 (0.66-1.41)	0.84
Roman Catholic	209	396	(52.8)	1.24 (0.97-1.57)	0.084	255	533	(47.8)	0.98 (0.80-1.21)	0.86
Pentecostal	370	667	(55.5)	1.26 (1.03-1.55)	0.028	661	1300	(50.8)	0.94 (0.80-1.11)	0.48
Apostolic	509	1007	(50.5)	1.03 (0.86-1.24)	0.74	716	1624	(44.1)	0.77 (0.66-0.90)	0.001
Islam	23	37	(62.2)	1.43 (0.71-2.86)	0.32	27	63	(42.9)	0.80 (0.47-1.36)	0.40
Zionist	13	25	(52.0)	1.23 (0.55-2.77)	0.62	31	57	(54.4)	1.00 (0.58-1.73)	0.99
Other	244	423	(57.7)	1.43 (1.12-1.81)	0.004	309	634	(48.7)	0.89 (0.73-1.09)	0.26
Marital status										
Currently married	1164	2146	(54.2)	1.04 (0.82-1.31)	0.77	1664	3244	(51.3)	1.13 (0.96-1.34)	0.14
Never married	851	1707	(49.9)	1		537	1343	(40.0)	1	
Divorced or separated	97	148	(65.5)	1.78 (1.18-2.66)	0.006	278	517	(53.8)	1.22 (0.96-1.54)	0.10
Widowed	39	73	(53.4)	1.52 (0.87-2.65)	0.15	278	625	(44.5)	1.20 (0.93-1.55)	0.17
Poverty quintile										
Poorest	177	384	(46.1)	1		247	553	(44.7)	1	
Second poorest	1013	1930	(52.5)	1.10 (0.88-1.39)	0.40	1117	2417	(46.2)	1.01 (0.83-1.22)	0.95
Third poorest	478	895	(53.4)	1.21 (0.94-1.57)	0.15	652	1321	(49.4)	1.01 (0.82-1.26)	0.91
Fourth poorest	457	813	(56.2)	1.50 (1.13-1.99)	0.005	697	1350	(51.6)	0.96 (0.76-1.21)	0.73
Least poor	26	52	(50.0)	1.09 (0.60-1.99)	0.79	44	88	(50.0)	0.99 (0.61-1.59)	0.95
Relationship to 15-24yr woman										
Parent	177	298	(59.4)	1.51 (1.15-1.99)	0.003	497	889	(55.9)	1.34 (1.13-1.60)	0.001
Sibling	482	890	(54.2)	1.20 (1.01-1.42)	0.037	653	1353	(48.3)	1.14 (0.99-1.31)	0.066
Uncle or aunt	107	204	(52.5)	1.07 (0.79-1.43)	0.67	199	373	(53.4)	1.25 (1.00-1.56)	0.053
Grandparent	31	81	(38.3)	0.77 (0.47-1.27)	0.31	131	345	(38.0)	1.05 (0.79-1.39)	0.75
Spouse or regular partner	280	446	(62.8)	1.30 (1.01-1.68)	0.045	-	-	-	-	-
Unrelated	1074	2155	(49.8)	1		1276	2769	(46.1)	1	
Community role										
Chief or Headman	26	46	(56.5)	1.45 (0.79-2.67)	0.23	6	8	(75.0)	4.09 (0.80-20.9)	0.090
Church leader	34	75	(45.3)	0.74 (0.46-1.19)	0.20	173	334	(51.8)	1.16 (0.92-1.46)	0.21
Teacher	24	50	(48.0)	0.68 (0.36-1.27)	0.22	43	71	(60.6)	1.19 (0.72-1.98)	0.49
Doctor or nurse	2	3	(66.7)	1.47 (0.13-16.7)	0.76	12	16	(75.0)	2.99 (0.94-9.49)	0.063
Village healthworker	0	2	-	-		22	25	(88.0)	8.69 (2.55-29.5)	0.001
Other	36	58	(62.1)	1.50 (0.86-2.61)	0.16	12	18	(66.7)	2.04 (0.75-5.56)	0.16
None	2029	3840	(52.8)	1		2489	5257	(47.3)	1	
CBO participation										
Yes	973	1828	(53.2)	1.05 (0.92-1.20)	0.49	1809	3784	(47.8)	0.98 (0.87-1.10)	0.70
No	1178	2246	(52.4)	1		948	1945	(48.7)	1	
HIV status										
Uninfected	1853	3555	(52.1)	1		2279	4849	(47.0)	1	
Infected	210	331	(63.4)	1.59 (1.24-2.04)	<0.001	348	604	(57.6)	1.33 (1.11-1.60)	0.002
Unknown	88	188	(46.8)	0.76 (0.56-1.03)	0.080	130	276	(47.1)	0.92 (0.71-1.19)	0.52

* Odds ratios from fully-adjusted multivariable logistic regression models.

Table S8 Comparison of community members' views on acceptability of condom use in marriage by socio-demographic characteristics, Manicaland, Zimbabwe, 2018-2019

Characteristic	Males					Females				
	Condom use in marriage (agreement)			Test for difference		Condom use in marriage (agreement)			Test for difference	
	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p	n	N	(%)	aOR* (95% CI)	p
Age-group										
15-19	226	1029	(22.0)	1.25 (0.96-1.62)	0.10	299	1184	(25.3)	0.87 (0.70-1.09)	0.22
20-24	122	693	(17.6)	1	-	261	1043	(25.0)	1	-
25-29	84	485	(17.3)	1.09 (0.79-1.52)	0.60	178	551	(32.3)	1.36 (1.07-1.72)	0.011
30-34	73	352	(20.7)	1.50 (1.02-2.19)	0.038	226	596	(37.9)	1.63 (1.29-2.05)	<0.001
35-44	134	623	(21.5)	1.48 (1.02-2.14)	0.040	377	946	(39.9)	1.56 (1.25-1.95)	<0.001
45-54	113	426	(26.5)	1.75 (1.16-2.64)	0.007	234	592	(39.5)	1.49 (1.15-1.92)	0.002
55+	102	466	(21.9)	1.42 (0.92-2.19)	0.12	230	817	(28.2)	1.20 (0.90-1.61)	0.22
Residence										
Village	278	1282	(21.7)	1	-	775	1916	(40.4)	1	-
Agricultural estate	359	1247	(28.8)	1.53 (1.25-1.89)	<0.001	395	1151	(34.3)	0.71 (0.60-0.84)	<0.001
Small town	177	950	(18.6)	0.86 (0.68-1.09)	0.20	426	1654	(25.8)	0.46 (0.39-0.55)	<0.001
City (high density)	40	595	(6.7)	0.29 (0.20-0.44)	<0.001	209	1008	(20.7)	0.38 (0.30-0.47)	<0.001
School education										
None	23	90	(25.6)	1	-	34	170	(20.0)	1	-
Primary	136	562	(24.2)	0.83 (0.48-1.42)	0.49	446	1368	(32.6)	1.60 (1.07-2.41)	0.023
Secondary	650	3190	(20.4)	0.75 (0.45-1.27)	0.29	1211	3883	(31.2)	1.66 (1.09-2.51)	0.018
Higher	45	232	(19.4)	0.75 (0.40-1.44)	0.39	114	308	(37.0)	2.14 (1.31-3.49)	0.002
Church										
Protestant	195	954	(20.4)	1	-	430	1355	(31.7)	1	-
Traditional	2	3	(66.7)	12.1 (1.06-137)	0.044	1	36	(2.8)	0.10 (0.01-0.72)	0.023
None	111	562	(19.8)	0.84 (0.63-1.12)	0.24	40	127	(31.5)	1.02 (0.68-1.55)	0.92
Roman Catholic	96	396	(24.2)	1.28 (0.96-1.71)	0.088	169	533	(31.7)	0.96 (0.77-1.20)	0.71
Pentecostal	123	667	(18.4)	0.94 (0.72-1.22)	0.62	367	1300	(28.2)	0.94 (0.79-1.12)	0.50
Apostolic	230	1007	(22.8)	1.09 (0.86-1.37)	0.47	534	1624	(32.9)	1.06 (0.90-1.26)	0.46
Islam	11	37	(29.7)	1.22 (0.57-2.60)	0.61	22	63	(34.9)	1.11 (0.64-1.93)	0.72
Zionist	6	25	(24.0)	1.90 (0.69-5.20)	0.21	15	57	(26.3)	0.90 (0.48-1.67)	0.74
Other	80	423	(18.9)	1.02 (0.75-1.38)	0.90	227	634	(35.8)	1.22 (0.99-1.51)	0.057
Marital status										
Currently married	426	2146	(19.9)	0.55 (0.40-0.74)	<0.001	1079	3244	(33.3)	0.86 (0.71-1.03)	0.10
Never married	371	1707	(21.7)	1	-	383	1343	(28.5)	1	-
Divorced or separated	35	148	(23.6)	0.73 (0.45-1.18)	0.19	161	517	(31.1)	0.72 (0.56-0.94)	0.015
Widowed	22	73	(30.1)	0.84 (0.45-1.58)	0.60	182	625	(29.1)	0.64 (0.48-0.85)	0.002
Poverty quintile										
Poorest	69	384	(18.0)	1	-	191	553	(34.5)	1	-
Second poorest	488	1930	(25.3)	1.47 (1.09-1.98)	0.010	823	2417	(34.1)	1.07 (0.87-1.31)	0.53
Third poorest	174	895	(19.4)	1.25 (0.90-1.74)	0.18	417	1321	(31.6)	1.15 (0.92-1.45)	0.22
Fourth poorest	110	813	(13.5)	1.13 (0.78-1.63)	0.53	352	1350	(26.1)	1.14 (0.89-1.47)	0.30
Least poor	13	52	(25.0)	1.92 (0.93-3.95)	0.077	22	88	(25.0)	1.05 (0.61-1.81)	0.85
Relationship to 15-24yr woman										
Parent	79	298	(26.5)	1.17 (0.85-1.60)	0.33	367	889	(41.3)	1.15 (0.96-1.37)	0.13
Sibling	142	890	(16.0)	0.66 (0.53-0.83)	<0.001	370	1353	(27.3)	0.91 (0.78-1.07)	0.26
Uncle or aunt	36	204	(17.6)	0.64 (0.43-0.94)	0.022	113	373	(30.3)	0.92 (0.72-1.18)	0.52
Grandparent	11	81	(13.6)	0.51 (0.26-1.03)	0.059	90	345	(26.1)	0.81 (0.59-1.10)	0.17
Spouse or regular partner	83	446	(18.6)	0.95 (0.69-1.32)	0.77	-	-	-	-	-
Unrelated	503	2155	(23.3)	1	-	865	2765	(31.3)	1	-
Community role										
Chief or Headman	11	46	(23.9)	1.15 (0.57-2.34)	0.69	3	8	(37.5)	1.54 (0.36-6.66)	0.56
Church leader	14	75	(18.7)	1.03 (0.56-1.90)	0.93	97	334	(29.0)	0.82 (0.63-1.06)	0.13
Teacher	15	50	(30.0)	1.70 (0.83-3.47)	0.15	23	71	(32.4)	0.67 (0.39-1.15)	0.15
Doctor or nurse	-	-	-	-	-	7	16	(43.8)	1.25 (0.44-3.12)	0.67
Village healthworker	-	-	-	-	-	12	25	(48.0)	1.55 (0.67-3.58)	0.31
Other	13	58	(22.4)	1.38 (0.72-2.64)	0.33	3	18	(16.7)	0.38 (0.11-1.35)	0.13
None	801	3840	(20.9)	1	-	1660	5257	(31.6)	1	-
CBO participation										
Yes	363	1828	(19.9)	0.90 (0.76-1.06)	0.20	1243	3784	(32.8)	1.04 (0.91-1.18)	0.55
No	491	2246	(21.9)	1	-	562	1945	(28.9)	1	-
HIV status										
Uninfected	732	3668	(20.0)	1	-	1469	4989	(29.4)	1	-
Infected	113	348	(32.5)	1.80 (1.38-2.33)	<0.001	327	673	(48.6)	2.15 (1.80-2.57)	<0.001
Unknown	9	58	(15.5)	0.85 (0.40-1.82)	0.68	9	67	(13.4)	0.45 (0.22-0.91)	0.028

* Odds ratios from fully-adjusted multivariable logistic regression models.

FIGURE S1 Variation in divergence from the social norm against teenage daughters having access to condoms: adjusted odds ratio (aOR) and 95% percent confidence interval for approval of condoms being made available for young people in schools by community location, relationship to an AGYW, and socio-demographic characteristic, Manicaland, Zimbabwe, 2018/2019

A Men

B Women

